

FATIGUE OF CARBON/GLASS AND CARBON/KEVLAR HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This is a study of the fatigue behaviour of hybrid composites of carbon/Kevlar-49 (C/K) and carbon/glass (C/G). A comparison is presented of the properties of uni-directional (ud) composites and laminates with a $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$ structure. The ud C/K composites have been tested in repeated tension and tension/compression at R ratios between +0.1 and -1.2. All other materials have been tested in repeated tension fatigue only (R = 0.1). Analysis of the results in terms of the fatigue ratio and strain life diagrams shows that there is substantial similarity between the response of ud and $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$ samples of both families. The ud results for the C/K system are analyzed in terms of a fatigue function which permits the representation of all data in a single two-parameter fatigue curve.

OBJECTIVES AND PROCEDURES

The fatigue response of a composite is a complex phenomenon linked with micro-failure mechanisms and the accumulation of damage, and it is not obvious how the fatigue behaviour of a CFRP laminate will be modified by the incorporation of a second species of reinforcement. We present results for two families of hybrids, carbon/Kevlar-49 and carbon/glass, in which the fatigue characteristics of the two second components (viz. KFRP and GRP) differ markedly both from one another and from the primary (CFRP) component⁽¹⁾. The materials were ply-by-ply C/K hybrids, with a 914 epoxy matrix, and C/G hybrids, with a 913 epoxy matrix, both containing Courtauld XAS carbon fibres. Most tests were on ud samples with compositions between CFRP and KFRP on the one hand and CFRP and GRP on the other. For comparison some tests were also carried out on plain CFRP, plain GRP, plain KFRP, and 50/50 C/K and C/G hybrids with a $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$ layup. The stacking sequence for these laminates was $[(\pm 45)_X, (0)_C, (0)_X, (\pm 45)_C, (0)_X, (0)_C]_s$ X being either Kevlar-49 or glass. Fatigue samples were straight-sided, 20mm wide and 2mm thick, with a test length of 100mm between tabs: they were conditioned to a moisture content of approximately 1% prior to testing.

The ud C/K composites were subjected to constant load cycling at R ratios ($\sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max}$) from +0.1 to -1.2, anti-buckling guides being used for tests involving compression. Most fatigue tests on the ud C/G composites and on $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$ laminates were at an R ratio of +0.1 (ie no compression component). All fatigue tests were carried out under load control at cycling rates between 3 and 8 GPa.s⁻¹.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

1. Mechanical properties

The composition dependence of modulus, E, strength, σ_t , and failure strain, ϵ_f , of the two families of ud hybrids are shown in fig. 1. The moduli in each case are linear functions of composition and the tensile strengths are adequately predicted by the

failure strain model⁽²⁾ (upper pair of lines in fig.1) The tensile properties of the $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$ laminates are shown in table 1.

Fig 1. Mechanical properties of ud composites

Table 1. Properties of $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$ C/K and C/G Laminates.

Composite	E GPa	σ _t GPa	ε _f %
914/XAS carbon	81.1	1.28	1.39
CFRP/KFRP(50:50)	52.7	0.81	1.51
914/Kevlar-49	33.1	0.64	1.82
913/XAS carbon	76.0	1.17	1.47
CFRP/GRP(50:50)	51.7	0.82	1.82
913/glass	23.9	0.71*	2.11

* measured at the same testing rate as the fatigue tests.

The stress/life ($S/\log N_f$) curves for the hybrids have been published elsewhere^(3,4). Those for the ud materials tested in repeated tension ($R = +0.1$) are characterized by a reasonable amount of scatter of data, but the $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$ results are much less variable. The patterns of behaviour appear complex, but analysis suggests that the distributions of results for both families of hybrids fall into uniform patterns determined substantially by (a) the monotonic tensile strength, which in neither case varies linearly with hybrid composition (fig.1), (b) the proportions of the constituents and their particular fatigue characteristics, and (c) the R-ratio of the fatigue cycle. In order to assess the effects of the second component in the hybrid, it is necessary to analyze the raw $S/\log N_f$ data in a variety of ways, particularly since stress/life curves do not always represent the most important or relevant design criterion.

2. Strain/life diagrams

When the stress/life data are normalized relative to the composite modulus, the results then represent curves of initial strain, ϵ_i , (or strain range, $\delta\epsilon_i$, for tension-compression cycles) vs life. In such plots (fig.2) there is a high degree of superposition, within the limits of experimental scatter, of results for both sets of hybrids, regardless of composition, of R-ratio (for the ud C/K group), and of lay-up (ie ud or $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$). Only the results for the plain GRP and the plain KFRP samples fall outside the main scatterbands for all other compositions. Such a result suggests some kind of synergistic effect since it appears that the presence of the carbon, in whatever proportion, eliminates the high slopes of the plain GRP and plain KFRP strain/life curves⁽¹⁾. This superposition makes it possible to predict the stress/life diagram for any member of either hybrid family, for whatever R ratio. In stating this we assume that had the C/G laminates been tested in cycles that included a compression component, they would not have behaved differently from the C/K family, since the response of a plain GRP laminate to compression is unlikely to be worse than that of plain KFRP. Differences in strength and stiffness resulting from the incorporation of the 45° plies do not seem to change the fatigue behaviour of the hybrids of either family.

3. The fatigue ratio

We have shown^(3,4) that, in stress/life terms, the fatigue stresses for a given life are linear with composition for ud C/K composites, but not for the ud C/G materials. However, this comparison does not yield a complete picture. In both hybrid families the strength is controlled by local failure mechanisms and is satisfactorily predicted by the failure strain model⁽²⁾ with a minimum in the strength vs composition curve when tensile failure strains of the two components differ. If, therefore, the fatigue responses of the two hybrid families are compared by normalizing the constant life

Fig 2. Strain/life curves for all composites, R ratio = +0.1; unidirectional composites - a) C/G hybrids, b) C/K hybrids
 [(±45,0₂)₂s] laminates - c) C,G and 50:50 C/G d) C,K and 50/50 C/K.

data relative to the monotonic tensile failure stress (measured at the same rate of deformation as in the fatigue tests), ie. in terms of the conventional fatigue ratio, the two families of hybrids show almost identical response (fig.3), and in both cases there is a marked positive deviation from linearity. Thus, the factors which determine monotonic strengths are not simply carried over into cyclic loading response. Furthermore, the fatigue ratios at 10⁶ cycles for the two 50:50 [(±45,0₂)₂s] hybrids are 0.72 (C/K) and 0.73 (C/G), almost identical with the common value of 0.75 for the two ud materials of 50:50 composition in fig.3, and they therefore show approximately

Fig 3. Fatigue ratio as a function of hybrid composition; ud C/K and C/G hybrids. R = 0.1; life = 10⁶ cycles.

Fig 4. Transmission of monotonic tensile strength into fatigue response, (see text for explanation).

the same level of "synergism". It is of course not valid to describe this as a synergistic effect, in the absence of a mechanistic model of hybrid fatigue failure against which to assess the actual result.

The extent to which the hybrid strengths are reflected in their fatigue response may also be assessed by comparing the measured tensile and fatigue strengths of, say, all hybrids of 50:50 composition with the means of the equivalent values for the single-fibre composites. If the fatigue stress for the plain CFRP laminate for a given life, N , is taken as $(\sigma_c)_N$, and that for the second component is $(\sigma_x)_N$, then the mean value, $(\sigma_{c,x})_N$, is

$$(\sigma_{c,x})_N = \frac{1}{2}[(\sigma_x)_N + (\sigma_c)_N]$$

If the corresponding experimental value for the hybrid laminate is $(\sigma_H)_N$, then the extent to which the fatigue resistances of the separate components are translated into the hybrid, using the linear combination (mixtures) rule as a basis for comparison, is indicated by the ratio $[(\sigma_H)/(\sigma_{c,x})]_N$. The value of this ratio as a function of life (derived from the original $S/\log N_f$ curves in refs 3 and 4) is given for ud and $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ of both families of hybrids in fig.4. All four curves start from about the same point, i.e. at a monotonic strength level some 80% of the means for the single fibre composites. For the C/G laminates, both curves rise markedly with number of cycles, the ud curve more rapidly than that for the $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ laminate. The implication is that the fatigue resistance increases with increasing life, and is better than could have been predicted from ordinary mechanical properties. In the case of the C/K composites, the ud results are similar to those of the ud C/G, although the increase is less marked and the improvement is subsequently reduced beyond the point when the plain KFRP fatigue response begins to deteriorate⁽¹⁾. The curve for the $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ material shows no improvement with increasing life, but it shows the same deterioration beyond about 10^5 cycles as the ud material. Thus, the ud C/K fatigue resistance, like that of the C/G composites, also increases with increasing life, up to a point, whereas the introduction of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies is clearly a more seriously limiting factor.

Fig 5. Constant life diagram showing the effect of mean stress on the fatigue response of ud C/K hybrids. The alternating stresses plotted represent the peak stresses for failure in 10^5 cycles. The broken lines at 45° represent the limits for tensile failure⁽³⁾.

Fig 6. Master curve for ud C/K hybrids (37.5% and 50% Kevlar); $R = -0.1$, $f = 0.81$.

4. Fatigue life prediction

The detailed effect of R ratio on the $S/\log N_f$ curves of the individual ud C/K composites may be presented in the form of a Constant Life diagram (fig.5). There is a measure of symmetry in this figure in the curves for each hybrid although not about the σ_{alt} axis. This uniformity leads us to develop a fatigue life prediction method for the C/K hybrids⁽⁵⁾ based on a parametric analysis of the data. The analysis is based

on postulation of an empirical interaction curve of the form:

$$f = a[(1 - m)(c + m)]^{-1}$$

where f is a stress parameter dependent upon the alternating and mean stresses (σ_{alt} and σ_m) and on the tensile and compression strengths of the materials, σ_t and σ_c , respectively. In this equation, $m = \sigma_m/\sigma_t$, $a = \sigma_{alt}/\sigma_t$, and $c = \sigma_c/\sigma_t$. Fig.6 shows an estimated curve to fit the data for the 37.5% and 50% Kevlar hybrids at 10^5 cycles from the data in fig.5 with f equal to 0.81. This f parameter, together with data from the $S/\log N_f$ curve, may then be used to derive a universal fatigue curve that shows promise as a life prediction model. Data for the whole family of hybrids may be represented in a single two-parameter fatigue curve, with the obvious result that design data for untested members of a hybrid family may be deduced from a more limited testing program. From the original fatigue data and the measured values of σ_t and σ_c , the data are reduced in accordance with the stress parameter formula and a typical example is shown in fig.7 for the C/37.5%K hybrid, 7a containing the original results and 7b the rationalized version. Further analysis⁽⁵⁾ leads to the use of the parameter f , together with empirical constants obtained from fatigue data, to derive best-fit stress/life curves through the rationalized data, as in fig.7b. The group of parameters needed to define the curve vary to a relatively slight degree with C/K ratio, which suggests that the pattern of behaviour of a complete family of hybrids can be predicted from a limited amount of data. In general the data seem to merge into one band, albeit with significant scatter. The results therefore justify the development of the stress parameter, f , and its use in examining the trends of fatigue behaviour in a systematic manner.

Fig 7. Fatigue results for C/37.5%K composites: a) original fatigue data, b) rationalized data.

CONCLUSIONS

■ Studies of the fatigue behaviour of unidirectional and $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ laminates of two families of hybrid composites have given conventional stress/life data that appear to fall into relatively simple patterns in relation to composition.

■ Two kinds of normalization procedures have been used to compare the behaviour of the two kinds of hybrids and of the two different structures. The first is to plot strain/life curves and the second is to normalize relative to tensile strength (ie. the fatigue ratio). The two methods emphasize slightly different aspects of behaviour, but by and large both give indications that hybridization of CFRP with either Aramid or glass fibres offers potential benefits in respect of fatigue response that are not in any way predicted by the ordinary mechanical properties of the hybrid composites. Thus, the glass and Kevlar offer a degree of protection of the carbon fibres, an effect that is well recognized on a grosser scale in the utilization of "softening strips" of GRP as crack stoppers in CFRP structures^(6,7).

■ A novel fatigue parameter has been defined that rationalizes the data on the Goodman diagram for ud C/K hybrid composites. With the help of this parameter a universal fatigue curve has been devised that shows promise as a valid life-prediction model.

■The results suggest that the problems of designing with hybrids for a fatigue environment may be somewhat simpler than might otherwise be expected, since interpolation appears to carry no hidden dangers.

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